

recorded less reduction in TDM and yield percentages under low light.

Physiologically efficient restorers, such as IR19058-107-1, Vajram, ARC11353, Jagannath, and Mahsuri, may be effective in developing superior medium- and late-maturing rice hybrids for subdued-light areas. □

Fertility alteration in photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) rice in response to photoperiod and temperature

Zhang Ziguo and Zeng Hanlai, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan 430070, China

The altered fertility of PGMS rice is generally considered to be induced by photoperiod. The sterility of PGMS rice is not always stable during long-day conditions, however, which makes it difficult to use.

We observed the spikelet fertility percentage of the original PGMS line Nongken 58S and of some derived lines under different photoperiod and temperature conditions. We conducted the experiments during 1990 and 1991 by stages. The plants were grown in phytotrons from panicle initiation to heading, about 20-25 d. We observed the fertility percentage 30 d after heading of japonica photoperiod-sensitive sterile lines selfed Nongken 58S and 63343, indica photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines W7415S and W6154S, indica check Guangluai 4, and japonica check Mudanjiang 8 (see table).

Results suggest that there is no absolute photoperiod-sensitive sterility or thermosensitive sterility for fertility induction in the sterile lines from Nongken 58S. The fertility alteration of PGMS rice is regulated by both photoperiod and temperature conditions and is a result of interaction between them.

When the temperature is above the critical sterility point (CSP) of 32 °C for Nongken 58S, pollens become sterile; when temperature is below the critical fertility point (CFP) of 22 °C for Nongken 58S, pollens become fertile regardless of the photoperiod length. Photoperiod-

sensitive fertility can be induced in the temperature range from CSP to CFP (TRPS). Only in TRPS is the pollen fertility alteration of PGMS regulated by photoperiod conditions. Even within TRPS, however, temperature conditions can still affect critical light length (CLL) and the degree of fertility alteration: when CLL becomes shorter, fertility decreases under short-day conditions as the temperature rises; when CLL becomes longer, fertility increases under short-day conditions as the temperature decreases.

The conditions for the sterility gene expression and the intensity of interaction between photoperiod and temperature differ among male sterile lines. Those

conditions determine whether a line is adaptable and can be used in rice production. CFP causes sterility fluctuation under long-day conditions. If the CFP of a sterile line being used in hybrid seed production is not low enough, a low temperature may cause it to self-fertilize. If the CSP is not high enough, it is very difficult to multiply the sterile line in short-day seasons under high temperature conditions.

CLL and the intensity of the interaction effect between photoperiod and temperature control the adaptability of a line. A line with a longer CLL could be used in high latitudes and a line with a shorter CLL could be used in low latitudes. A line with a larger interaction

Spikelet fertility % of PGMS rice under various conditions.

Temp (°C)	Fertility (%) at given daylength (h:min)						
	13:00	13:20	13:40	14:00	14:20	14:40	15:00
<i>Nongken 58S583^a (japonica, photoperiod-sensitive)</i>							
22	25.4	23.8	21.6	19.1	24.6	26.5	24.7
24	61.8	57.7	43.5	24.6	18.5	7.9	1.7
26	54.6	45.9	32.1	7.5	0.0	0.0	0.0
28	42.8	32.7	12.4	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
30	21.5	12.3	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>6334S^a (japonica, photoperiod-sensitive)</i>							
22	29.6	24.1	21.8	21.8	26.7	25.3	23.8
24	57.5	43.8	36.6	26.5	17.6	11.0	5.6
26	53.6	42.4	23.8	7.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
28	34.7	25.1	10.6	1.2	0.0	0.0	0.0
30	11.9	8.6	1.5	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>W7415S^b (indica, photoperiod-insensitive)</i>							
22	16.4	15.8	21.2	18.5	18.5	21.6	17.6
24	43.3	38.6	25.6	23.7	25.8	23.8	24.7
26	34.6	5.8	5.3	4.9	4.2	2.6	3.8
28	0.8	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0
<i>W6154S^b (indica, photoperiod-insensitive)</i>							
22	19.4	16.9	17.9	21.5	21.8	23.0	19.5
24	56.8	49.5	29.6	27.8	30.6	28.5	28.7
26	43.2	24.8	15.4	20.1	17.9	12.8	16.4
28	1.3	0.0	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.2
<i>Mudanjiang 8 (check 1, japonica)</i>							
22	37.4	35.8	41.9	41.2	42.3	42.9	42.0
24	67.9	65.9	71.2	74.2	67.9	67.5	64.3
26	67.6	64.6	64.9	70.2	67.9	65.3	64.0
28	65.4	65.9	71.0	65.4	66.8	54.9	61.8
30	51.8	50.7	49.6	46.7	43.5	41.8	40.6
32	32.3	31.9	29.7	27.5	25.9	24.6	24.7
34	6.5	3.7	3.2	2.8	2.2	1.9	1.4
<i>Guangluai 4 (check 2, indica)</i>							
22	25.4	25.9	27.9	30.4	31.8	32.5	31.3
24	56.8	54.5	53.9	56.8	54.2	57.8	57.2
26	72.0	76.3	7.4	68.9	70.6	71.0	71.5
28	67.9	67.4	71.9	75.3	68.5	68.1	65.4
30	56.8	61.5	54.3	53.8	51.0	50.6	48.4
32	42.9	42.0	39.6	35.6	38.7	34.7	32.5
34	7.4	5.7	4.3	4.8	5.2	2.3	2.8

^a Values were zero at 32 and 34 °C. ^b Values were zero at 30, 32, and 34 °C.

effect between photoperiod and temperature could be adapted to wider areas because a high temperature can complement the insufficiency of

photoperiod in low latitudes and a longer photoperiod can complement the inefficiency of temperature in high latitudes. The ideal type of sterile line for

hybrid rice production has a low CFP, a high CSP, a wide TRPS, and a high intensity of supplementary effect between light and temperature. □

The relationship of photosensitivity and sterility in photosensitive genic male sterile (PGMS) lines

Zhang Ziguang and Zeng Hanlai, *Agronomy Department, Huazhong Agricultural University, Wuhan, Hubei 430070, China*

PGMS rice was first discovered in a field of Nongken 58S, a photoperiod-sensitive japonica variety. Photoperiod controls both the development and the pollen fertility of Nongken 58S. Most PGMS lines were photoperiod-sensitive; photoperiod-insensitive sterile lines derived from Nongken 58S became thermosensitive sterile lines. We wanted to breed PGMS lines that are photoperiod insensitive to flowering induction.

We crossed Mudanjiang 8, a photoperiod-insensitive variety, with Nongken 58S. We selected sterile plants with short growth durations from the F₂. From the F₉, we selected the sterile line E85S. We planted it and its parents in 1990 under short day (SD) 10 h light/d, and long day (LD) 14.5 h light/d conditions to observe growth duration and pollen fertility percent (see table).

E85S is insensitive to photoperiod for flowering induction as is Mudanjiang 8, and is sensitive to photoperiod in its fertility alteration, like Nongken 58S. These results indicate that different genes control photosensitive sterility and photosensitive flowering induction and they can be recombined in new types of PGMS lines. □

Fertility and photosensitivity of E85S and its parents. China, 1991.

	Nongken 58S	Mudanjiang 8	E85S
SD heading promotion rate ^a	38.5	-3.4	2.0
Photoperiod sensitivity	Strong	Weak	Weak
Days from sowing to heading with at least 14.5 h of light/d	104	59	58
Maturity type	Late	Early	Early
Fertile pollen (%)			
In SD	70.2	77.4	65.6
In LD	0.0	76.8	0.0

$$^a\text{SD heading promotion rate} = \frac{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD} - d \text{ from sowing to heading in SD}}{d \text{ from sowing to heading in LD}} \times 100.$$

Identification of CMS lines for hybrid rice development under northern Indian conditions

M. P. Pandey, J. P. Singh, S. C. Mani, H. Singh, S. Singh, and D. Singh, *Plant Breeding Department, G. B. Pant University of Agriculture and Technology, Pantnagar 263145, Uttar Pradesh (UP), India*

We evaluated 13 cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines for adaptability and stability for pollen sterility under the subhumid tropical conditions of western UP in northern India. V20 A, which originated from China, and IR62829 A and IR58025 A, which originated from IRRI, were obtained from the Directorate of Rice Research, Hyderabad. PMS-1 through PMS-10 originated from Punjab Agricultural University (PAU), Kapurthala. We planted 5-row plots of each line on 16 Jul 1991 under strict isolation, using *Sesbania* spp. as a physical barrier. Data were recorded for

Performance of CMS lines at Pantnagar, India, during 1991 wet season.

CMS line	Days to 50% flowering	Plant height (cm)	Pollen sterility (%)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Stability
V20 A	81	72.6	100.0	100.0	Stable
IR62829 A	93	71.7	99.7	99.1	Needs purification
IR58025 A	99	81.0	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-1	109	64.1	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-2	102	63.6	100.0	99.7	Stable
PMS-3	109	70.8	98.4	99.9	Unstable
PMS-4	113	64.8	99.4	99.9	Needs purification
PMS-5	113	66.0	100.0	100.0	Stable
PMS-6	114	66.2	98.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-7	109	74.6	95.1	100.0	Unstable
PMS-8	109	64.4	100.0	99.9	Stable
PMS-9	113	79.0	86.2	100.0	Unstable
PMS-10	107	69.5	100.0	100.0	Stable

days to 50% flowering, plant height, percent pollen sterility, and percent spikelet fertility, for which we used the mean of 25 panicles.

We identified several stable CMS lines with varying duration and plant type (see table). V20 A, IR58025 A, PMS-1 A, PMS-2 A, PMS-5 A, PMS-8 A, and PMS-10 A had complete pollen sterility and almost 100% spikelet sterility. In

contrast with earlier observations, IR62829 A had slight fertility of pollen and spikelets, possibly because of a different seed source.

These stable lines all had very short stature (63.6-72.6 cm), except IR58025 A, which had semidwarf stature (81.0 cm). V20 A had early duration, IR58025 A and PMS-2 mid-early, and others, medium to mid-late. Observations at